

Digitalization Changed the World of Transportation Bounce a Modern E-Transport Mode

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Abstract

The concept of digitalization has been playing a important role in all sectors of the economy. It is mainly concerned with providing better services to customers along with an opportunity to gain more shortly. The Transportation sectors are achieving tremendous growth in recent years, which is because of the digitalization of transportation. Transportation technology primarily works on GPS facility. This paper has an objective of understanding the functioning of Bounce and the consumer perception towards the digitalization of transit concerning Bounce scooters.

Keywords: Digitalization, Recommendations, Quality reasons, Competitors.

Introduction

Technological innovation in the transportation industry has enabled businesses to improve the quality of their services. Technology helps in improving the reliability of public transportation networks by providing visibility on arrivals/departures or route information for travelers for a hassle-free journey. Modern transportation is currently experiencing changes thanks to transformative transportation technologies. ITS(Intelligent transportation system)is an emerging system that is comprised of an advanced information and telecommunication network for users and roads and vehicles. They provide travelers with information while improving the safety and efficiency of the transportation system. The modern transportation system has the edge over the traditional transportation system has provided the following benefits:

- Saves cost
- Increases efficiency
- Lack of human error
- Safer data storage in the cloud
- Reduces operational costs
- Enables data to be analyzed.

Profile of Bounce Scooters

It is a Bangalore based start-up. Vivekananda Hallekere started Bounce in Bangalore. Bounce provides transportation facility for travelling on daily basis. It is economical. It saves time and it does not create stress for the user. Bounce provides unique facility like picking up the scooter, using it and leaving it anywhere.

Bounce uses IoT-(internet of things) enabled technology to track its bikes. Bounce functions in over ten cities and given the rapid growth in the bike-taxi segment, it straight away competes with the likes of Vogo, Rapido, RentOnGo, Zip-Hop, ONN Bikes, and others.

The original name of Metro bikes is Bounce. Bounce which was operating in the city of Bangalore and was started in the year 2014 and it was working in the similar manner. At present 30000 and above riders are using Bounce facility throughout 24 hours in a day. Bounce currently swash of a fully serviced fleet of 5000+ dock-less scooters that can be used round the clock by anyone through their app, at extremely moderate rates. The vehicle uses a unique hardware which was built with IoT-technology. It helps the users unlock the bikes with keyless technology, drive it to where they wanted in the city, and drop it off at their destination, wherever that may be.

Bounce charges Rs. 5 per kilometer and that is quite economical. The bounce app is made available on IOS and Android platforms. Bounce report shows that more than 20000 interested customers have downloaded the app. For the expansion program of bounce all over India they have raised debt funding of \$3 million lead by debt-financing firm InnoVen Capital. Bounce is able to make profit as it has a very interesting pricing model which is as follows: the cost of petrol works out to Rs 1.75 to Rs 2 per km and maintenance to Rs 1.5 per km. It works out to over Rs 4 per km. If you charge anything above that you start making Re 1 for every kilometer.

Challenges faced by Bounce Scooters

- Fuel Costs.
- Business Process Improvement.
- Improved Customer Service.
- Economy.
- Driver Shortage & Retention.
- Government Regulations.
- Environmental Issues.
- Technology Strategy & Implementation.

STP Model used by Bounce

- S-Segmentation
- T-Targeting
- P-Positioning

Segmentation: It consists of the following features.

- **Demographics:** Gender: male and female Age: 18-35, Focus on youth, Income: Middle-class, Buyers: Student and professionals.
- **Psychographics:** Time- saving, Convenient, Pocket- friendly, mobility solutions, navigation facility available, easy to use.
- **Geographically:** Available in metro cities and urban areas, more accessible : near the metro station and stops.
- **Behavioural:** One can use Bounce by registering for one time. The facility is available for all 24 hours and original and hard copy of document are not required, and payment can be done using any digital mode.

Targeting

Target customers are students and professionals. Focus on youth and educated respondents using the internet (e-wallets). It helps to track the trip and also can check the history trips. Customers can earn rewards with applicable Terms and conditions.

Positioning

Pick and drop anywhere is the tagline of Bounce, which allows users to rent gearless scooters and motorbikes from designated pickup points across the city and drop them off at any fixed locations at the end of the ride. It is the best and most economical way to get around town especially with the traffic

Documents to be submitted for using Bounce

For renting the bikes, the following documents are required:

1. Driving Licence for National and International drivers.
2. Aadhaar or Mail id for national and copy of passport for international.
3. For students the documents required are original college ID and Aadhaar.

Procedure to Rent a Keyless Scooter (Steps)

Step 1: Download the Bounce bike app on Play Store or IOS

Step 2: Open the app, find your nearest yellow scooter

Step 3: Pick your ride, add a destination, choose the payment mode and confirm the booking

Step 4: Walk to your two-wheeler, enter OTP on the keypad and start your bike ride

Step 5: After your ride, park your bike at the closest legal parking area and then end your trip.

ADD-ONS

1. Every scooter provides helmets in their trunk. Press the green button for opening.
2. Zero deposit and minimum documentation.
3. All your bike rides are insured.
4. Get on road-assistance anytime, anywhere, for your rental scooter.

Unique Features of Bounce

1. Keyless and dock-less bikes.
2. Hassle-free, designed for your convenience.
3. Most affordable ride in town
4. Safety assured.
5. Easy payment options
6. One-click login.

Diverse Options of Bounce

1. Short rides using keyless scooters
2. Long-distance rides with scooters
3. Bikes from top brands
4. Bounce is also available in: Bangalore, Hyderabad, Mysore, Jaipur, Gokarna, Manipal, Belgaum, and more.

Financial Report of Bounce

The keyless bike-sharing portal was successful in raising fresh capital, its losses for the year ending 31-3-2018 has almost doubled.

According to its RoC (Registrar of the company) filing for financial year 2017-18, the investment has increased from Rs 4.3 crore to Rs 5.4 crore from last year. The company losses also increased from Rs 3.2 crore to Rs 7 crore.

Future Plan of Bounce

However, the team can further decrease this cost, and that is where electric vehicles come into the picture. The cost of electricity significantly reduces the total price to Rs 0.5 per kilometre, the bounce can increase the charges from Rs 2 to Rs 3 per kilometre which allows the bounce to make profit. The firm is presently looking to increase more electric vehicles and is working with different vendors and partners for the same.

Objectives of the Study

- To understand how E-transportation works.
- To study the functioning of Bounce.
- To study consumer perception towards Bounce.
- To provide recommendations and suggestions for improvement in the services given by Bounce.

Sources of Data Collection

In two different ways, the data is collected. They are as follows:

1. **Primary Data Collection** : A structured questionnaire was prepared to gather the opinion of the respondents towards Bounce.
2. **Secondary Data Collection**: Published and Unpublished information was collected.

Data Analysis And Interpretation

1) Graph showing the age of the respondents

Interpretation 1

Out of the total respondents, 78.9% are in the age group of 18 to 25, and 17.8% are in the age group of 25 to 35, 3.3% are in the age group above 35 age.

2) The respondent's background is shown in the Graph

Interpretation 2

58.9% are students, 21.1% are working professionals, and 20% are employees.

3) Graph showing Awareness about Bounce

Interpretation 3

90% of respondents are aware of the existence of Bounce.

4) Graph showing about the Usage of Bounce Facility

Interpretation 4

Out of the total respondents, 73.3% use the bounce facility.

5) Graph Showing the Responses of the Respondents Regarding Safety

Interpretation 5

From the above data, 86.7% of respondents think bounce is safe, and 13.3% of respondents believe it is not.

6) Reasons for using Bounce is represented in this Graph

Interpretation 6

16.7% of respondents use bounce as it is readily available, 14.4% of respondents use bounce as it is cost-effective, 16.7% of respondents use bounce as it is convenient, 52.2% of respondents use bounce for all of the above reasons.

7) Graph showing the offers attracted by Bounce

Interpretation 7

Cash-back offers attracts up to 36.7%, 16.7% of respondents are interested in good returns, 30% of respondents get attracted by other facilities that are offered by Bounce.

8) From the above Graph it can be Inferred that users are Continuously using Bounce

Interpretation 8

90% of respondents would like to continue the bounce facility, and 10% of respondents discontinue the usage of bounce.

9) Graph showing the Recommendation of Bounce to others

Interpretation 9

85.6% of respondents like to recommend bounce to others.

10) Graph Showing Overall Quality of Bounce Facility

Interpretation 10

25.6% of respondents think bounce is excellent, and 60% of respondents think bounce is good.

11) Bounce Facility Ratings

Interpretation 11

48.9% of respondents gave a 4-star rating to the bounce

Findings

- The Majority of respondents are of 18-25 age groups.
- The Majority of students use bounce facilities when compared to working professionals and employees.

- The Majority of respondents are aware of the Bounce facility.
- The Majority of respondents use the Bounce facility.
- The Majority of respondents think Bounce is safe.
- The Majority of respondents think Bounce is available, cost-effective, and convenient.
- The Majority of respondents get interested in cash-back that is offered by Bounce.
- The Majority of respondents would like to continue the use of Bounce.
- The Majority of respondents like to recommend Bounce to others.
- The Majority of respondents say that the quality of Bounce is good.
- The Majority of respondents give four ratings to the Bounce.

Recommendations

- The Bounce Company should increase its advertisements and publicity.
- The Bounce Company should increase its security-related measures.
- The company should think about its cost-effectiveness for increasing its number of customers.
- The company should offer more points to referrers.
- The company should increase its quality provided by the bounce to its customers.

Conclusion

From the above-collected data, we can conclude that E- Transportation has found its place in the Indian market. The younger generation is the majority of users of the Bounce facility. There is stiff competition for Bounce, in spite of that Bounce has created awareness among the customers and attract the customers through their various offers. Bounce has a bright future if it can meet the challenges and implement a few of the above recommendations given in this paper. The future of E-Transportation has enormous scope. In the future; there an increase in demand for truck platooning, electric vehicles, autonomous driving, electric/hybrid buses, and smart transportation solutions.

References

1. <https://www.slideshare.net/princessanjali721/role-of-digital-india-in-enhancing-transportation>
2. <https://www.slideshare.net/SapnaDevi12/bounce-scooter>
3. https://bouncesharecom/?gclid=EAIaIQobChMIpfCs8_3S5QIVSRSPCh3EywPSEAAAYASAAEgIj5PD_BwE
4. https://www.business-standard.com/article/companies/bengaluru-s-bounce-becomes-world-s-fastest-growing-bike-sharing-start-up-119073100559_1.html